

QUEST AS MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN EDUCATION

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ANNOTATION

The article focuses on the use of webquest technology in the modern educational space. Webquests can help create learning motivation during classroom as well as extracurricular activities. Helps develop critical thinking skills.

Today, students freely use information and communication technologies technologies (hereinafter referred to as ICT) in their daily life and educational activities.

Unlimited access to the Internet, the use of smartphones, tablets make the process of obtaining information is simpler and more accessible. On the other hand, the network.

The Internet not only provides enormous opportunities for students' self-development, but it also creates certain difficulties. Students often encounter problems when selection of reliable sources of information, their analysis and comparison, because modern the information environment sometimes represents a "global dump" where one can come across resources containing quite contradictory and not always plausible information.

The teacher must adapt to changing circumstances and skillfully use the advantages of modern ICT for the benefit of the educational process. It is no coincidence that one of the conditions for the implementation of general education is the creation modern information and educational environment, which includes, among other things, the system modern pedagogical technologies that ensure successful learning in it.

In particular, webquest technology allows you to successfully integrate the Internet into educational activities, leading students away from consumer attitudes

to information and the Internet, contributes to the achievement of both personal and subject and meta-subject results. This technology makes it possible to achieve important educational results:

- personal - the formation of motivation to learn new things and self-improvement, understanding the possibilities of self-realization, revealing creative potential;
- meta-subject - development of communicative competence, work skills with information (search, selection, summarization of information, creation of a project, solving the task), self-organization, ability to perform different social roles, user computer skills;
- subject - acquiring new knowledge and applying it in academic subjects situations, the formation of a scientific type of thinking.

The developers of the webquest are Bernie Dodge and Tom March, professors University of California at San Diego. The technology is relatively not new. First webquests appeared in 1995, and are now one of the main means of forming communicative and ICT competencies of students. The webquest involves creating problem task with elements of a role-playing game, for which you use Internet resources.

Educational technology web quest provides great opportunities for implementing project activities both in class and in extracurricular activities. It can be used both as part of immersion in the subject and as part of binary lessons.

The webquest helps to search for Internet information on the instructions of the teacher, develops students' computer skills and improves their vocabulary, and encourages them to learn independently of the teacher. Students perceive the task as something "real" and "useful", which leads to increased learning efficiency.

Forms of organizing training sessions

1. Search and processing of information

- writing an abstract review
- review of the site on the topic
- analysis of existing abstracts on the Internet on this topic, their evaluation
- writing your own version of the lecture plan or its fragment
- compilation of bibliographic list
- preparation of a fragment of a practical lesson
- preparation of a report on the topic
- preparation of a discussion on the topic
- work with a web quest prepared by a teacher or found on the Internet

A Web quest is a specially organized type of research activity, for which students search for information on the Internet at specified addresses. They are created in order to make better use of students' time, to use the information received for practical purposes and to develop the skills of critical thinking, analysis, synthesis and evaluation of information.

For this work to be as effective as possible, a web quest (a specially organized web page) must contain the following parts:

1. Introduction, which describes the timing and sets the initial situation.
2. An interesting task that can actually be completed.
3. A set of links to network resources necessary to complete the task. Some (but not all) resources can be copied to the site of this web -quest to make it easier for students to download materials. These resources must contain links to web pages, e-mail addresses of experts or thematic chats, books or other materials available in the library or teacher. By indicating exact addresses when completing assignments, students will not waste time.
4. Description of the work process. It should be divided into stages with specific deadlines.
5. Some explanations for processing the information received: guiding questions, concept tree, cause-and-effect diagrams.
6. A conclusion reminding students what they learned by doing the activity; perhaps ways for further independent work on the topic or a description of how the experience gained can be transferred to another area. Web quests can be short-term or long-term. The goal of short-term projects is to acquire knowledge and integrate it into your knowledge system. Working on a short-term web quest can take from one to three sessions. Long-term web -quests are aimed at expanding and clarifying concepts. Upon completion of work on a long-term web -quest, the student must be able to conduct a deep analysis of the knowledge gained, be able to transform it, and master the material enough to be able to create tasks for work on the topic. Work on a long-term web quest can last from one week to a month (maximum two).

Web quests are best suited for work in mini-groups, but there are also web quests designed for individual students. Additional motivation when completing a web quest can be created by asking students to choose roles (for example, scientist, journalist, detective, architect, etc.), and act in accordance with them: for example, if the teacher suggested the role of the Secretary of the United Nations, then this a character can send a letter to another participant (who plays

the role of the President of Russia, for example) about the need for a peaceful resolution of the conflict.

A Web quest can concern one subject or be cross-disciplinary. The researchers note that in the second case, this work is more effective.

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